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ASALARI OILALARINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI

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Annotasiya. Maqolada asalari oilalarining mahsuldorligi, asal va mum yetishtirishi hamda ularning iqtisodiy samaradorligi kabi ko‘rsatkichlar o‘rganildi va qiyosiy tajribalar asosida tahlil qilindi.

Kalit so‘zlar: asalari, shakar sharbati, asal, mum, perga, ishlab chiqarish, ish haqqi, gulchangi, ona asalari, tuxum, xarajatlar, sof foyda rentabillik, iqtisodiy samaradorlik.

Аннотация. В статье на основе сравнительных экспериментов были изучены и проанализированы такие показатели, как продуктивность пчелиных семей, производство меда и воска, а также их экономическая эффективность.

Ключевые слова: пчела, сахарный сироп, мед, воск, перга, производство, зарплата, пыльца, пчеленая матка, яйца, затраты, рентабельность, чистая прибыль, экономическая эффективность.

Abstract. In the article, based on comparative experiments, such indicators as the productivity of bee colonies, the cultivation of honey and wax, as well as their economic efficiency were studied and analyzed.

Keywords: bee, sugar syrup, honey, wax, perga, production, salary, pollen, queen bee, eggs, costs, profitability, net profit, economic efficiency.

KIRISH

Toshkent viloyatining tog‘ oldi sharoitida asalarichilikni rivojlantirish, oilalar mahsuldorligini oshirish bugungi kunning dolzarb masalalaridan biridir [1,2,3,4].

Bozor iqtisodiyotining o‘ziga xos xususiyatlaridan biri – ishlab chiqarilayotgan asalarichilik mahsulotlari salmog‘i va sifati bilan jahon andozalari talabiga mos kelishi lozim [5,6,7,8].

Asalarichilikda asosan ishlab chiqarish xarajatlarini kamaytirish yo‘li bilan ko‘plab sifatli mahsulot yetishtirish, daromad va sof foyda salmog‘ini oshirish imkonini yaratish talab etiladi [9,10,11,12].

Asalarichilikda o‘tkazilayotgan ko‘pgina tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatmoqdaki, asalari oilasi mahsuldorligini oshirish uchun erta bahorda ona asalari yetishtirish, asalari oilalarini shakllantirish va asalari paketlari ishlab chiqarish, ularni jadal usullarda boqish va iqtisodiy samaradorlikni oshirish asosiy omil hisoblanadi [13,14,15].

Shu maqsadda, asalari oilalarini tezkor texnologiya asosida boqish, ularni tog‘ oldi sharoitida oila mahsuldorligini oshirishga ta‘sir etadigan texnologiyani ilmiy asoslarini o‘rganish to‘g‘risida ilmiy tadqiqotlarni o‘tkazish muhimligidan dalolat beradi [16,17].

TADQIQOTNING MATERIALI VA USLUBI.

Tadqiqotlar 2023-2024 yillarda Toshkent viloyatining Bo‘stonliq tumanidagi Yangi Qurg‘on MFY “Safinabonu-Mexrangiz” MChJning asalarichilik xo‘jaligi va Soyliq MFY “Al-Baxrom Soxibkorlar” fermer xujaligi asalarizorlarida olib borildi.

Tadqiqotlar davrida bir xillik asosida tajriba va nazorat guruhlari tashkil etildi.

Olingan ma'lumotlarga Styudent mezonlari yordamida, Ye.K. Merkureva (1970, 1991) uslubini bo'yicha, (R) qiymat darajasiga ko'ra statistik ishlov berildi, hisob-kitob ishlari MS OFFICE (Microsoft Excel) dasturlari bo'yicha kompyuterda korrelyatsiya qilindi.

TADQIQOT NATIJALARI.

O'tkazilgan tadqiqot ishlarimiz natijalarini ishlab chiqarishga joriy etish maqsadida, ularning iqtisodiy samaradorligini o'rganish ham muhim ahamiyatga ega. Biz shu maqsadda olib borgan tadqiqot ishlarimizning iqtisodiy samaradorligini o'rgandik.

Shuning uchun ham asalari oilalarini ko'chirib turish jarayonlariga alohida e'tibor berildi, ularning asal to'plash imkoniyatlaridan samarali foydalanildi. Tajribadagi asalari oilalarining o'sish va rivojlanishidan fermer xo'jaligining o'zidagi barcha sharoitlar hisobga olindi. Bunda bitta asalari oilalarini tashkil etishda va uni ko'chirib turishdagi sarf - xarajatlar hisoblab borildi 1-jadval.

Asalari oilalarining shakar sharbati bilan ozilantirish **3600000** so'm sarf - xarajat qilindi, jami xarajatlar miqdori **20054520** so'mni tashkil etdi. Asalari paketlarini hozirgi kundagi sotish bahosi 350 - 400 ming so'mni tashkil etishini hisobga olsak, oddiygina har bir asalari paketlari sotgan taqdirda ham ulardan qo'shimcha ravishda yana minglab so'mni sof foyda qilish mumkin.

1- jadval

Bitta asalari oilasidan olingan mahsulotlarning iqtisodiy samaradorligi.

№	Ko'rsatkichlar	Bir kunlik 1 ta asalari oilasiga beriladigan miqdori, mg	Tajribadagi oilalar soni	90 kun mobaynida 1 ta oilasiga beriladigan miqdori, kg	Xarajat miqdori so'm
1	Shakar sharbati (250x90=2,25x10=22,5)	250	10	225	225x16000=3600000
2	Asal (200x90=18x10=180)	200	10	180	180x85000=15300000
3	Perga (0,069x90=6,21)	0,069	10	6,21	6,21x1200=74520
4	Asalarichiga ishxaqqi (12000x90=324000)	12000	10	108000	1080000
	Jami xarajatlar				20054520
5	Asal ishlab chiqarish kg (26,7x10=267)	26,7	10	267	267x85000=22695000
6	Gul changi gr (2x10=20)	2	10	20	20x6000=120000
	Jami, so'm				22815000

7	Yalpi foyda:				22815000- 20054520=2760480
8	Rentabillik darajasi %				2760480x100/20054520=13,8

1 - jadval ma'lumotlaridan ko'rinayaptiki, har bitta asalari oilasi 26,7 kgdan kg tovar asal olindi. Faqatgina asalni sotishdan olingan foyda **22695000** so'mni tashkil etdi (o'rtacha bir kg asal 85000 so'mdan sotildi). Har bitta asalari oilalarini tashkil etish uchun qilingan sarf - xarajatlar (**20054520** so'm) chegirib tashlanganda sof foyda **2760480** so'mni tashkil etdi. Asalari oilalaridan foydalanishning rentabellik darajasi 13,8 % - ni tashkil etdi.

XULOSA

Ilmiy - tadqiqot ishlari shuni ko'rsatdiki, Toshkent viloyatining tog'oldi hududlari sharoitida asalari oilalarida bahorgi asalari paketlarini tashkil etish samarali ekanligini ko'rsatdi. Bu esa o'z navbatida nafaqat zootexnikaviy va iqtisodiy, balki aholini asal maxsulotiga bo'lgan ehtiyojini qondirish borasida olib borilayotgan bir butun chora - tadbirlarini asosi hisoblanadi.

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